

Refrasort: Automated sorting of refractory waste for high value recycling

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Abstract

High value recycling of refractories into the production of new refractories is currently limited due to a shortage of high purity raw materials. In current practice, at end-of-life different types of refractories are mixed resulting in material that is only suitable for low grade applications or landfilling. For high value reuse as refractory raw materials, the mixed refractory waste must be sorted into high purity fractions of distinct refractory types based on the chemical composition.

The ongoing European FP7 project REFRASORT aims to develop an automated sorting technology to separate up to 8 types of waste refractory bricks into pure material fractions under industrial conditions. The refractory types that are targeted represent > 90% of all shaped refractories, and fall into three main classes (magnesia-based, dolomite-based, alumina-based) with further subdivisions based on C and Al content. The REFRASORT system consists of

different steps, namely: 1) pre-treatment (dust and metal removal), 2) inlining, 3) identification and 4) mechanical sorting. This contribution focuses on the metal removal and identification steps.

As a result of the use and handling, a surface alteration layers is present on the spent refractory bricks. This layer, which is generally 100 – 200 µm thick but may reach up to 1 mm at surfaces that were in direct contact with the molten metal and slag, complicates the search for a suitable identification technique. Feasibility tests showed that most sensor techniques based on surface measurements, such as colour sensors, LIF, XRF and FTIR are not suited for reliable identification. The most promising technique for reliable identification of spent refractories was found to be the LIBS (Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy), but it too experiences difficulties to identify metal and C containing bricks due to the inherent properties of the spent refractories. Feasibility tests with a portal-type metal detector have shown promising results to sort out metal and C containing bricks simultaneously. These results are presented in this paper.

Introduction

Background and problem definition

The refractory production industry in Europe is vital for all high temperature processes, such as the production of metals, cement, ceramics and many others. Raw materials account for about 40 to 50% of the refractory costs and have a major influence on the quality of the finished products (Ducastel et al., 2015). The European industry is largely dependent on import, mainly from China, for high quality raw materials (PRE, 2009). Graphite and magnesite have been classified as critical raw materials by the European Commission (EC, 2014) and 95% of refractory grade bauxite is produced in China (PRE, 2009). The prices of refractory raw materials have risen significantly in the last decade, by 30 to over 300 percent depending on the raw material (Guéguen et al., 2014).

One way to reduce the supply risk and raw material costs is high value recycling of spent refractories into refractory production. However, these secondary raw materials must meet stringent quality criteria, as the raw material properties have a direct and indirect effect on important refractory properties (Guéguen et al., 2014). The spent refractories must be separated from impurities such as metal and slag, and classified into high purity fractions according to their chemical composition. For industrial application, whole bricks should be cleaned and sorted in an automated way. The ongoing FP7 project REFRASORT (www.refrasort.eu), funded by the European Commission, is developing a sensor-based sorting system for spent refractories, which combines sensor identification with mechanical sorting.

Spent refractory characteristics and challenges for recycling

Spent refractories pose significant challenges for sensor identification. First of all, an enormous variety of refractory materials is in use today, each tuned to the requirements set by a specific application. Within the REFRASORT project it was decided to focus on the steel industry, which is responsible for 60% of all refractory use worldwide (PRE, 2011). A selection was made of 8 types of refractories used in the steel industry that represent 90% of all shaped refractories, and which can be grouped into three main classes: magnesia-based, doloma-based and alumina-based (Table 1). Both fired (low C) and tempered (high C) bricks are included as well as samples with and without antioxidant. As such, the major challenges for identification are present in the selection.

Group	Type	Composition
MgO-based	Fired MgO (FM)	High MgO, no C, low CaO
	MgO-C with antioxidant (MCA)	High MgO, 5 – 15 wt-% C, low CaO, antioxidant (Al)
	MgO-C without antioxidant (MC)	High MgO, 5 – 15 wt-% C, low CaO, no metallic Al
Doloma-based	Fired doloma (FD)	High MgO, high CaO, no C
	Doloma carbon (DC)	High MgO, high CaO, 5-15 wt-% C
Alumina-based	Fired bauxite (FB)	High Al, Al/Si ~8/1, low CaO/MgO
	Fired andalusite (FA)	High Al, Al/Si ~2/1, low CaO/MgO
	Fired chamotte (FC)	High Al, Al/Si ~1/1, low CaO/MgO

Table 1: Properties of 8 refractory types studied in REFRASORT and their characteristic composition features

Refractories are subjected to harsh conditions during use. High temperatures and chemical attack result in severe weathering, especially at the surface in direct contact with the molten steel and slag, the so-called „hot face“. At end-of-life, current practice is to break out the refractories indiscriminately and transport them to recycling companies where they are sorted manually into low value streams. The breakout process generates additional dust, mainly due to the disaggregation of hydrated doloma bricks. As a result of the aforementioned processes, the spent refractories are typically covered with dust and reaction layers. These contaminated layers are generally 100 – 200 µm thick but may range up to several cms for bricks in direct contact with slag (Figure 1). For the C rich bricks, it was observed that oxidation leads to carbon depletion at the outer surfaces, which is again most noticeable at the hot face (Figure 2).

A small fraction (circa 5 %) of the spent refractories contains a significant amount of metal due to infiltration of molten steel. These metal infiltrations are diffusely spread and may penetrate up to several centimeters into the brick (Figure 3). Quantification of the metal impact is important to determine whether it is economically interesting to sort them out for metal recovery. In summary, the outer surfaces of spent refractories are not representative for the chemical composition of the bulk material. As such, reliable identification by traditional surface techniques such as colour sensors, Laser induced fluorescence (LIF), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Near infrared (NIR) and Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy is not feasible, as demonstrated in feasibility tests performed in the REFRASORT project (Knapp et al., 2015). Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS), discussed at this conference by (Conemann et al., 2015) can penetrate the surface contamination layers, and therefore has a high potential for use in this specific application. However, it also experiences difficulties to reliably determine the metal and C content due to its limited penetration capacity and the heterogeneous distribution of these components throughout the spent refractory bricks. Therefore, additional techniques were investigated specifically for these components, which are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 1: Dust and carbonation layers on outer surface of spent doloma. The photo's on the right are an excerpt from the photo's on the left (indicated by a white square). Arrows in the top photo's point to carbonation layers.

Figure 2: Decarbonisation layer at outer surface (hot face) of spent doloma carbon brick

Figure 3: Metal infiltration in spent refractory

Metal and C detection

Portal-type metal detector

Initial feasibility tests showed that a portal-type metal detector offers potential for detection of not only metal, but also C content in refractories. To explore this further, fresh refractories were crushed to < 5 mm size and mixed with varying amounts (0, 0.5, 2 and 5 m%) of metallic particles (stainless steel, < 5 mm). These mixtures were compacted into cylinders of 42 mm diameter using a force of 110 kN, resulting in a pressure of circa 800 bar. The cylinders were measured with a portal-type metal detector (Mesutronic 600/300). The coil of the metal detector has a width of 600 mm, a height of 300 mm and the electromagnetic field alternates at 150 kHz. As can be seen in Figure 4, a clear relationship exists between signal intensity and metal content for the alumina class refractories (FC, FA, FB) and MCA. However, the signal differs between different refractory types. For example, the signal for 5% metal is clearly lower in the FC than for the other types. For MCA, signal intensity is higher than expected for the

2% metal sample. This can be explained by the presence of 2-3% metallic Al in this refractory type, which may give an additional response. Furthermore, it is clear that the MC refractory gives very different signals. This is possibly related to the presence of high amounts of C, but it remains unclear why the same relationship is not observed for the MCA refractory. In any case, it is interesting to note that the metal detector can clearly distinguish between MC and MCA, despite the small differences in Al_2O_3 content.

From these preliminary results it can be concluded that matrix effects play an important role in the determination of metal and C content in these samples. Further experiments are therefore ongoing to compare metal and C content between samples with similar matrices.

Figure 4: Metal detector signal for selected refractories. Bubble size indicates % metal in the samples. X and Y axes represent factors calculated from electric and magnetic conductivity.

Microwave heating

A second technique that seems promising for the determination of C content in particular is heating by microwave. Fresh refractories were heated in a microwave (2.45 GHz) for 60 s at 700 W. After heating, the refractories were removed from the microwave and their temperature profile determined as a function of time after heating. The tests were performed in duplicate. Figure 5 shows the results for the magnesia based refractories. It is clear that the C-rich refractories (MC, MCA) have a much higher temperature profile than the refractory without

C (FM), likely related to a higher absorption of microwave radiation by the C that is present. It therefore seems that this technique has potential for identifying the carbon-rich materials. However, further tests are ongoing to determine the influence of metal content and matrix.

Figure 5: Temperature profile of fresh refractories after microwave heating for 60 s at 700 W

Conclusions and outlook

The REFRASORT project is developing an automated sorting system for spent refractory bricks based on sensor identification and mechanical sorting. The main identification sensor selected for application in the REFRASORT project is LIBS (Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy). However, additional sensors were investigated to determine metal and C content as the concentration of these substances at the surface of spent refractories is not representative for the bulk composition. A portal-type metal detector shows promising results for metal content, but further study is needed to eliminate matrix effects and determine its potential for the quantification of metal and C. This technique may also offer added value to distinguish between MgO-C bricks with and without antioxidant. Microwave heating has potential for identifying C-rich bricks, and will be tested further to evaluate metal and matrix effects.

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